

REIMAGINING THE WELFARE STATE

LIFETIME EQUAL OPPORTUNITY ENDOWMENT

A REPORT FOR THE LSE SCHOOL OF PUBLIC POLICY

August 2022

AUTHORS

ANA ABAD
BETHANY CARTER
PREBHJOT KAUR
YAXIN GUO

IN COLLABORATION WITH

MARIO FRANCESCOTTI

ABOUT THIS REPORT	3
PART I: INTRODUCTION.....	4
PART II: CURRENT GLOBAL AND DYNAMIC TRENDS AFFECTING OUR LIVES	5
Aging population	5
Increased labour force participation by women	5
Insecure work	5
Unskilled labour.....	6
Climate change	6
Backlash to globalisation	6
The need for a new welfare state	7
PART III: BASIC STRUCTURE OF THE NEW MODEL	8
Two-pronged approach: Basic provision + Lifetime Equal Opportunity Endowment (LEOE).....	8
How the LEOE would work.....	10
Conditions Applicable to All LEOE Accounts	12
Expected outcomes and long-term impact	14
PART IV: SPECIFIC ELEMENTS OF THE NEW MODEL	15
Education.....	15
Healthcare	19
Housing.....	24
Work Security	27
Pensions and Long-Term Savings	30
PART V: IMPLEMENTATION AND FEASIBILITY	35
Administrative feasibility.....	36
Political feasibility.....	40
PART VI: RECOMMENDED REINFORCING POLICIES FOR THE MODEL.....	41
Pre-redistribution policies	41
Taxation policies	41
Regulatory environment	42
Engaged populous	42
Happiness Index or Wellbeing Budget	43
PART VII: CONCLUSION	44

About this report

This report, funded and directed by LSE alum Mario Francescotti, seeks to inform the LSE project, *Reimagining the State: Renewing the Social Contract*. Led by the LSE School of Public Policy, this project aims to develop a 'London Consensus' on how to redesign the social contract globally to deliver equitable and inclusive growth in the post-COVID world.

This report focuses on the welfare state as one component of the social contract, offering a new model for welfare provision based on the principles described by Minouche Shafik in her book, *We Owe Each Other: A New Social Contract for a Better Society*.

The authors of this report are four LSE postgraduate students: Ana Abad, Bethany Carter, Yaxin Guo, and Prebhjot Kaur. The authors are completing the Master of Public Administration at the LSE School of Public Policy and conducted this analysis over seven weeks with support from Nick Rowley, Senior Lecturer in Practice at the School. The primary audience of the report is the LSE School of Public Policy and Professors Andrés Velasco, Tim Besley, and Ricky Burdett.

While the analysis and implications contained in this report are not exclusive to a particular region or country, it is most relevant and applicable to countries with well-developed welfare systems seeking to reform these systems to achieve greater equity and efficiency.

Part I: Introduction

The social contract can be understood as the collection of rules and norms governing the rights and obligations of individuals living together in a society. Minouche Shafik describes it in her book by the same name 'what we owe each other'.¹ While various social contracts have governed societies over time, the welfare state is a distinctly modern component of the social contract, arising as a response to the disruption and challenges posed by capitalism, industrialisation, and urbanisation beginning in the 18th century.²

Over this pivotal period, the Industrial Revolution ushered in unprecedented economic growth driven by productivity increases and severance of economic activity from the religious and social norms that once governed commerce and obligations within society. This radical economic transformation enabled significant improvements in living standards that would continue for the next two centuries. However, it also had major implications for the social contract, as pre-industrial systems of charity and mutual aid designed for small, rural communities were insufficient to address largescale urban poverty, particularly for the working poor.³

Eventually, recognizing the market failures within this capitalist system, collective action by unions, civil society, and reform-minded policymakers like William Beveridge, author of the Beveridge Report (1942), resulted in the introduction of various forms of state assistance not just for the poor but also for the middle class. Today, welfare policies, though varied in design, are a feature of all developed countries.⁴

As Minouche Shafik describes, growing inequality, civil unrest, political polarisation, and populism suggest society is currently undergoing transformation equally if not more disruptive than the Industrial Revolution, requiring a re-examination and reconfiguration of the welfare state to meet current challenges and adapt to new understandings and technologies. This report builds on the call to action in *What We Owe Each Other* (hereafter *WWOEO*) by proposing a radical new model for the welfare state designed for the 21st century.

¹ Shafik, M. (2021). *What we owe each other: a new social contract for a better society*. Vintage., pg. 2-3.

² Garland, D. (2016). *The welfare state: A very short introduction*. Oxford University Press., pg. 3.

³ Ibid.

⁴ Ibid.

Part II: Current Global and Dynamic Trends Affecting Our Lives

Technological developments, globalisation, and steady economic growth has led to higher living standards and ushered in new and dynamic challenges, with many countries around the world struggling to cope with their consequences. Some of these challenges are discussed below.

Aging population

Average life expectancy is on the rise due to improvements in living standards and health technology. As a result, the working population in some developed countries is not large enough to support care for the elderly population.⁵ Faced with this demographic challenge, many developed countries are struggling to adjust their health and pension systems to ensure adequate coverage for their populations within their current means.

This has fiscal implications but also consequences for human capital development. A longer life expectancy means many more working years requiring continuous upskilling to keep up with technological change and remain competitive in the workforce. As such, legacy education systems designed for 20th century economies and industries will need to adapt to provide for lifelong learning, adult education, and skills training.

Increased labour force participation by women

Women disproportionately undertake caring responsibilities and perform unpaid domestic labour. While the increased participation of women in the workforce has brought many benefits to society and is a welcome trend, it has implications for the division of childcare, elderly care, and domestic labour which need to be accommodated.⁶

Insecure work

Technological change has enhanced labour mobility across sectors and geographies as well as led to a rise in flexible working arrangements. The last few decades have seen a surge in economic migrants from low- and middle-income countries to high-income countries. This has led to increased participation in the workforce in host countries, especially in low-skilled work. However, the key challenge faced by host countries has been in ensuring their basic worker rights, protections, and pensions.

With the development of technology and mobility, work is increasingly characterised by temporary contracts, part-time arrangements, and 'gig' work. While these arrangements have their benefits, they are less secure. Europe is considered to have some of the most highly regulated labour markets, and yet one third of Europe's employees have 'alternative' contracts. These are often not entitled to benefits such as bonuses, profit sharing, overtime, training, and career development opportunities.⁷ Such flexible, non-traditional arrangements pose challenges to the funding and provision of pension and retirement income along with healthcare for this workforce.

⁵ International Labour Organization. (2018). *World Employment Social Outlook 2018*.

https://www.ilo.org/wcmsp5/groups/public/---dgreports/---dcomm/---publ/documents/publication/wcms_615594.pdf

⁶ OECD. (2019). *Women at Work in G20 countries: Progress and policy action*.

<https://www.oecd.org/g20/summits/osaka/G20-Women-at-Work.pdf>

⁷ *WVOEO*, pg. 98.

Unskilled labour

Technologies such as artificial intelligence (AI) and robotics have the potential to render a broad range of current jobs redundant, resulting in significant labour market disruption. Those with higher education are likely to be trained to upgrade their skills, whilst those undertaking repetitive work are more likely to be replaced.⁸

Climate change

One of the biggest challenges of our time is mitigating and adapting to climate change. Climate change is increasing the risk of extreme weather events and natural disasters all over the world and expected to make many places uninhabitable over the next few decades. This is likely to result in industry transformations, greater movement of people, increased economic risk and uncertainty, and even more extreme economic inequality.⁹

Backlash to globalisation

As evidenced by recent election cycles, the Western world has experienced a backlash against globalisation with a rise in populist politicians advocating for increased tariffs and against international trade, using anti-immigrant rhetoric, and weaponizing political ideology. This has led to countries seeking to defy international comparative advantage to become more self-reliant in important industries such as hydrocarbons, energy, food, and technologies like semiconductors. This, in turn, has made the global supply curve more inelastic and thus exposes the world to small changes in the demand curve leading to significantly larger changes in prices.

Much of the world is also now experiencing historically high inflation and cost of living increases as a result of the delay in paring back the expansive, demand-enhancing monetary and fiscal stimuli that accompanied the COVID-19 pandemic. Policymakers have failed to realise the extent to which the global supply curve has become inelastic.

The people most affected by this inflation are those on low and fixed incomes, exacerbating social and economic inequalities. Equally, recent attempts at reducing demand by tightening monetary and fiscal policy are also impacting those with the least opportunity. All these issues need to be addressed to effectively prevent further social and economic inequality.

Some political actors have adopted a zero-sum worldview focused on 'taking back' the resources and the prosperity that globalisation unleashed on major segments of the global economy and certain segments of the domestic economies. These populist messages are short-sighted and ultimately self-defeating (as witnessed by the effect on the global supply curve). In contrast to a politic of rage and envy, these high levels of discontent and anti-globalisation sentiment worldwide call for a form of globalisation that is more inclusive, better regulated, and focused on common prosperity and lifelong equal opportunity for all.

⁸ *WVOEO*, pg. 98.

⁹ Mercy Corps. (2021). The facts: How climate change affects people living in poverty. <https://www.mercycorps.org/en-gb/blog/climate-change-poverty>

The need for a new welfare state

David Garland, a historian of the Welfare State, has characterised the welfare state as an 'indispensable means of making capitalist economies socially and economically sustainable'.¹⁰ As Minouche Shafik argues, the current problems of social upheaval and polarisation, inequality, and environmental degradation are very likely signs that the welfare system is no longer fit for purpose. Thus, a new paradigm is needed to ensure access to lifelong equal opportunities for all and protect the population from the uncertainty of these new realities.

In light of the global trends described above, this report proposes a model for the welfare state (described in more detail in Part III) that will allow for greater individual responsibility, direction, and ownership over their share of welfare spending. The new model aims to be a more effective tool for mutual risk-sharing, building trust in government, and forming links of solidarity within a population.

As illustrated in Figure 1, this model is intended to be part of a larger social contract seeking to achieve the following five goals for all citizens: a fair start in life, bodily health and safety, empowerment over one's lifetime, security against risks and economic shocks, and generational equity. In accomplishing these goals, the model is informed by principles of compassion, mutual obligation, equity, flexibility/freedom, and transparency.

Figure 1: Goals and Guiding Principles

Source: Developed by the authors

¹⁰ Garland, D. (2016). The welfare state: A very short introduction. Oxford University Press., pg. 4.

Part III: Basic Structure of the New Model

The changes and challenges described in Part II will continue to shape our politics and way of life over the next few decades. The new welfare state must therefore enable us to tackle these dynamic and disruptive changes that are part of our daily lives and economic activity. The aim of the welfare model proposed in this report is to create equal opportunity for all across lifetimes and therefore will require bold changes to how governments currently spend on social benefits.

LSE Professor Nicholas Barr is referenced in *WWOEO* in characterising the current welfare state as ‘one quarter Robin Hood’ (redistribution of resources from rich to poor) and ‘three quarters piggy bank’ (mutual insurance).¹¹ Adding to this, Minouche Shafik emphasises the importance of the welfare state in achieving redistribution and insurance ‘over the course of our own lives’. This distribution of funds over one’s lifetime is referred to as ‘consumption smoothing’, one of three core functions of the welfare state, the others being poverty relief and insurance against adverse life events.¹²

Minouche Shafik argues that the global trends discussed in Part II make redistribution across one’s lifetime an increasingly important policy objective for the welfare state. However, the existing welfare model, designed for the industrial era, is not adequately structured to perform a comprehensive consumption smoothing function needed for a globalised, information-driven economy. For example, while there has been growing recognition of the importance of the first 1000 days of life and the need for continuing education, these areas do not feature prominently or consistently in the welfare state of many countries. It is this consumption smoothing function that the new model proposed seeks to address most directly.

Two-pronged approach: Basic provision + Lifetime Equal Opportunity Endowment (LEOE)

This report envisions a new welfare state with two essential components:

- A **first order, basic level of provision** of social goods and fundamental rights aimed at overcoming fundamental market failures and ensuring consistent, adequate provision of basic goods required for a healthy, productive life; and
- A second order provision in the form of a **Lifetime Equal Opportunity Endowment (LEOE)** to provide flexibility in welfare provision and lifelong equal opportunity to all citizens.

The first component encompasses basic public services and institutions that each society and government has agreed to as part of their existing social contracts. The provision of such basic services usually implies the existence of a market failure in the private market for those goods, necessitating government intervention. Examples of such basic services include access to adequate shelter, primary health care, and a basic education. This first component is the bone structure of the social safety net.

The second component of this new model is a national endowment inspired by the Singaporean Central Provident Fund (CPF) in combination with Thomas Piketty’s idea of an ‘inheritance for all’.¹³

¹¹ *WWOEO*, pg. 13.

¹² Nicholas Barr, personal communication, July 1, 2022.

¹³ Piketty, T. (2020). *Capital and ideology*. Belknap Press.

This per capita endowment would add an additional layer of protection on top of the basic social safety net with the goal of providing consumption smoothing benefits and thereby risk-protection and equal opportunity across one’s lifetime. This endowment, especially if coupled with cutting-edge technology, has the potential to reinvent the welfare state for the 21st century by balancing security with flexibility and mutual aid with individual responsibility. The endowment would give individuals the ability to customise their access to, and use of, the welfare system whilst guarding against fraud and abuse.

Both components can have ‘piggy bank’ and ‘Robin Hood’ elements, depending on the country context and the degree to which the endowment is financed through general taxation, mutual insurance, individual contributions, and employer contributions.

In addition to these two complementary core components of the new welfare state, governments could implement at their discretion additional policies to reinforce the underlying core model. These policies would be tools for providing additional flexibility or policy exceptions, incentivising certain positive behaviours or disincentivising negative behaviours, and generating virtuous cycles. Examples of such policies will be discussed in further detail in subsequent sections of the report.

This three-tier structure is visualised below.

Figure 2: Conceptual Structure of New Welfare State Model

Source: Developed by the authors

How the LEOE would work

The Lifetime Equal Opportunity Endowment (LEOE) is an annual endowment from birth provided by the government for all citizens and permanent residents of a country. The exact structure and benefit level of the endowment would be configurable to each country's norms and values, fiscal position, and appetite for social spending.

To provide an example of this endowment in practice, Figure 3 models how an endowment of €5,000 per year may be distributed to and used by a person over the course of their life with the following underlying assumptions:

1. Each person would have an individual LEOE account linked to a personal digital ID and managed by a centralized government agency.
2. Each person would manage their own accounts once they turn 18; prior to 18, their legal guardian would be responsible for their account.
3. The government would provide a set endowment annually to the individual from birth.
4. The individual would have the choice whether to spend the endowment each year or save it for large expenses later in life, with certain conditions designed to balance short-term need with long-term consumption smoothing.
5. While the illustration below assumes no additional private savings, a goal of the model is to incentivise increased personal savings, and therefore accounts are expected to hold a greater balance across the lifespan.

Figure 3: Example of Yearly Endowment

Source: Developed by the authors

Expenditure would vary over the course of one's life with five distinct spending accounts embedded within the endowment:

1. Education
2. Healthcare
3. Housing
4. Work security
5. Pensions and long-term savings

Initially, the endowment would be divided across these areas according to default percentages stipulated below. Then the individual can transfer between accounts or to other individuals, with some conditions. All funds in the LEOE would be either cash or inflation index-linked bonds so that their value is not eroded by inflation. The housing account and pension and long-term savings account would have some flexibility on the type of investments that the individual wishes to hold. For example, capital in the primary home or domestically oriented mutual funds for further growth in their pension and long-term savings account.

Table 1: Organisation and growth of accounts

	Education	Healthcare	Work security	Housing	Pension & long-term savings
Suggested default % of annual endowment <i>(Could vary based on age per the CPF model in Singapore)¹⁴</i>	30%	20%	20%	20%	10%
Investment type	Cash & index linked bonds				
Ability to change investments	N/A			Capital investment into primary residence	Domestically oriented mutual funds
Risk of the investments	Low	Low	Low	Low except for capital invested in first home	Sliding scale of risk (<i>higher when younger</i>)
Ability to withdraw	Can be withdrawn at any time for use on accredited courses with no tax penalties	Can be withdrawn up to annual cap with no tax penalties		Can be withdrawn at any time for use on accredited institutions with no tax penalties	Cannot be withdrawn until retirement (or only in certain exceptional circumstances)
Timeline of investments	Inflation-linked investments			Long-term investments	

Source: Developed by the authors

¹⁴ Central Provident Fund of Singapore (2022). https://www.cpf.gov.sg/content/dam/web/member/fag/growing-your-savings/documents/CPF_Allocation_Rates_from_1_January_2022.pdf

Conditions Applicable to All LEOE Accounts

To make the LEOE work and avoid abuse, the following are 12 basic conditions that would apply to all LEOE accounts, though countries may choose to implement additional rules.

1. No eligibility criteria

There should be no income or behavioural conditionalities to receive the endowment. All citizens would receive the payment regardless of income level, employment status, or a specific behavioural requirement.

Similarly, while the LEOE would be primarily for citizens, governments could choose to extend eligibility for LEOE accounts to permanent visa holders or temporary migrants, should circumstances call for wider provision.

2. Minors would rely on their legal guardian to manage their account

Each person's LEOE account would be linked to their legal guardian until the age of 18. The legal guardian would be responsible for managing the child's account including spending and savings. Upon turning 18, the individual would become responsible for their own account.

3. Spending conditionalities

The yearly endowment could only be used in the five designated spending categories (education, healthcare, housing, work security, and pensions and long-term savings) with the goal of encouraging behavioural shifts to build wealth and improve risk and opportunity management.

Conditions on expenditure could be monitored through an accreditation process managed by the centralised government agency to ensure the appropriate use of funds and quality of services, such as those of education institutions or healthcare providers.

4. Restricted accessibility in some situations

There may be situations in which access to funds would be restricted. For instance, a country may choose to restrict funds if a person is incarcerated but continue the accumulation to ensure equal opportunity at a better life when the person is released from prison. Likewise, additional conditions could be applied to the use of those funds upon release to incentivise positive decisions and reduce the probability of recidivism.

5. Governments may use the model to deliver fiscal policy (top-ups)

In bad economic conditions, governments frequently provide financial stimulus in the form of direct cash transfers or subsidies. The LEOE could be a useful vehicle for providing such economic relief through top-ups to LEOE accounts. This would enhance governments' ability to deliver stimulus more quickly and in a more targeted fashion.

6. Targeted assistance

Governments typically also provide benefits to people unable to work due to disability or lifelong illness to ensure equal opportunity in life. This model could provide for such assistance through a higher endowment for people with disability or lifelong illness.

7. End of life and permanent emigration

Individuals could designate another individual or non-profit organisation to receive any funds remaining in their accounts upon death or permanent migration out of the country by completing a beneficiary form. This condition reaffirms an individual's ownership of their own LEOE funds. If the funds, however, are not claimed for an extended period of time as stipulated by LEOE regulations or a beneficiary form is not completed, the funds may be forfeited to the state.

8. Individuals are able to transfer funds between accounts, as well as to other individuals up to a yearly capped amount.

In addition to choosing whether to spend their annual endowment or allow it to accumulate year over year, individuals would also have the option to transfer their funds between the five stipulated accounts freely, with the exception that no funds should be withdrawn from the pensions and long-term savings account. This would encourage personal responsibility while allowing individuals to flexibly customise their use of the endowment.

Transferring funds to other individuals would provide further flexibility that some families may need to meet their social or caring responsibilities. For instance, a parent may want to add additional funds to their child's education account, a daughter may want to supplement her parents' pension account, or an individual may want to help a friend cover the cost of a procedure through their healthcare account. Rather than treating each recipient as an atomised unit responsible only for themselves, this flexibility would encourage responsible sharing of resources whilst guarding against moral hazard.

The individual would need to nominate a set number of beneficiaries for these potentially larger transfers. Transfers to individuals that have not been nominated as beneficiaries should have an annual cap of 10-15% of the account's total balance, excluding the pensions and long-term savings account, to minimise the risk of abuse.

9. Tax-free expenditure

Funds spent from the healthcare account and the education account would not be subject to sales tax.

10. Additional voluntary contributions will be encouraged to supplement the endowment

There would be no limits on additional voluntary contributions by individuals into any account as the LEOE aims to increase personal savings. Furthermore, voluntary contributions could be incentivised through government or employer matching schemes. This would help the private sector share responsibility with the government for welfare mechanisms that are ultimately related to productivity and work, such as unemployment benefits, childcare leave, and parental benefits. For example, the state could build in incentives such as matched contributions for childcare expenses.

11. Abuse avoidance

To reduce the possibility of abuse of funds, alternative forms to cash could be used within the LEOE model, such as rebates upon proof of spend, vouchers and/or tax credits. Pay-outs could also be limited, for example, to 80% of qualifying expenses (i.e., 20% co-payment) instead of the entire expense to encourage individual responsibility and prevent abuse of the system. Additionally, while technology would enable basic self-management of LEOE accounts, there could be case managers to provide expert advice and review and approve exceptional uses of funds.

12. Online portal

To operationalise this model, we envision the use of an online portal for individuals to access and manage their LEOE accounts similar to online banking. This portal could also serve educational purposes, linking accountholders to information about their funds, resources for making informed decisions, and tools for tracking and maximizing their account usage. Such a portal would rely on the centralised system of digital IDs described previously and require robust data privacy and security protections.

Expected outcomes and long-term impact

Logic models can be helpful in visualising a programme’s proposed activities, evaluate the path from activities to outcomes, and test assumptions. Figure 4 shows a logic model linking the inputs and activities of the model with its expected outputs, outcomes, and long-term impact. The outcomes have been divided into those experienced by government as an institution and the individual or society more broadly. Whilst we recognize country-specific dynamics and implementation considerations are of significant concern (and the subject of further research) this logic model can serve as a starting point for such discussions.

Figure 4: Logic Model for New Welfare State Model

Source: Developed by the authors

Part IV: Specific elements of the new model

To provide further detail on the operation of the LEOE, this section delves into each of the five spending accounts within the LEOE, drawing on evidence of developed welfare states primarily in Europe.

Education

Introduction

Education, being essential to personal and economic development, is a central pillar of the social contract of most countries. The first 1000 days of our life are some of the most important for cognitive, physical, and emotional development. Primary and secondary education prepares us for life's challenges, unlocks opportunity and empowers us to pursue our passions. Tertiary and vocational education fulfils a vital economic role: it equips the future workforce with the skills they need to be productive.

Given the ever-evolving, complex global economy described in Part II, the ideal education system should strive to provide lifelong equal learning opportunities for everyone. Most European countries invest heavily in pre-school, primary, secondary, and tertiary education. However, some important stages in the education system require further attention to address the trends and challenges of the 21st Century. These include early childhood, adult education and retraining, and vocational education.

Currently, significant investment is made in primary and secondary education whilst pre-primary and continuous adult learning receive the lowest levels of funding.¹⁵ By the age of six, the human brain reaches 90% of its adult volume, making this a critical stage for significant learning.¹⁶ Early childhood education therefore plays a crucial role in equalising lifetime opportunity in laying the foundation for later success in school, career, and life.¹⁷

As mentioned in Part II, technological developments and our longer working lives are changing the structure and form of the labour market. Many repetitive and simple skills are being replaced by technology. This beckons the need for lifelong reskilling opportunities that are inexpensive and appropriate for re-entering the workforce.

For example, Singapore's 'Skills Future' programme provides each citizen with \$500 at age 25 to spend on continuing education courses or trainings to help them improve their skills and develop their potential throughout life, regardless of their starting point.¹⁸ Furthermore, the government assists in the design and offering of a range of course offerings to support them at different stages in their careers. France and Italy also have similar models in place.¹⁹

¹⁵ *WWOEO*, pg. 55-56.

¹⁶ OECD. (2020). Early Childhood Education: Equity, Quality and Transitions. <https://www.oecd.org/education/school/early-childhood-education-equity-quality-transitions-G20.pdf>

¹⁷ Ibid.

¹⁸ The RSA. (2021). Piloting a new approach to lifelong learning. <https://www.thersa.org/blog/2021/03/piloting-a-new-approach-to-lifelong-learning>

¹⁹ Ibid.; OECD. (2021). Provincial Centres for Adult Education (pg. 32). https://www.oecd.org/els/emp/skills-and-work/adult-learning/CPIA_What_how_who.pdf

Basic Provision: Primary and Secondary Education

Our model begins with publicly provided primary and secondary education, a key component of the welfare state worldwide, including all Europe. Some European countries also subsidise tertiary education partially or fully. Table 2 below outlines the basic public provision of some European countries at each stage of education that we envision may remain.

Table 2: Examples of government-funded education in Europe

	Childcare	Pre-primary	Primary & Secondary	Higher Education	Adult Education
Italy	✓ <i>(Free from 8:30am – 12:30pm)</i>	✓	✓	✓	✓
France	✓	✓	✓	✓ <i>Highly subsidized</i>	✓
Poland	✗ <i>There are publicly-funded and private nurseries and you have to pay for both but the rates differ substantially.</i>	✓ <i>Extra hours will be charged.</i>	✓	✓	✗ <i>The main providers of 'out-of-school' continuing education in Poland are Continuing Education Centres and Practical Training Centres.</i>
United Kingdom	✓ <i>England: 570 hours of free childcare for 2-year-olds. Scotland: Up to 1,140 hours of funded early learning for 2-year olds. Wales: 487 hours of free childcare a year for 2 & 3 year olds living in disadvantaged areas.</i>	✓ <i>In different parts of the UK, all children aged 3 and 4 are entitled to a certain number of hours per year of free early education or childcare.</i>	✓	✗ <i>England, Wales, Northern Ireland</i>	✗
	✗ <i>Northern Ireland: No free childcare between the ages of 0-3.</i>			✓ <i>Scotland</i>	

Sources: (1) The Scottish Government. (2013). Early Childhood Education and Care Provision: International Review of Policy, Delivery and Funding. <https://www.gov.scot/publications/early-childhood-education-care-provision-international-review-policy-delivery-funding/pages/4/>; (2) Employers for Childcare. (2022). Is free childcare available in Northern Ireland?. <https://www.gov.scot/publications/early-childhood-education-care-provision-international-review-policy-delivery-funding/pages/4/>; (3) Italian Ministry of Education. (2022). Educational system of education and training. <https://www.miur.gov.it/web/guest/sistema-educativo-d-istruzione-e-formazione>; (4) Bulgarelli, D. (2022). Quality of employment in childcare, Country report: Italy. European Public Service Union. <https://www.epsu.org/sites/default/files/article/files/Country%20report%20Italy%20childcare.pdf>; (5) Euraxess Poland. (2022). Childcare and education. <https://www.euraxess.pl/poland/information-assistance/childcare-and-education>; (6) Polish Eurydice Unit. (2020). The System of Education in Poland. <https://www.eurydice.org/pl/wp-content/uploads/2021/01/The-system-of-education-in-poland-online-new.pdf>

LEOE Education Account

The LEOE education account would be a top-up scheme to supplement the public education system. This account would enable governments to encourage learning for all, adapting the strategy to the national context and economic situation of the country. Given primary and secondary education is provided publicly at no or very little cost in most European countries, the LEOE education account would strive to provide access to important extra-curricular and educational activities that are not publicly provided.

The LEOE education account would have a digital system facilitating its operation. The following steps would be required to navigate the education account:

1. The LEOE central authority would make publicly available and regularly update a list of educational programmes accredited by the government. Providers would include both public and private institutions and course offerings would be varied.
2. An individual could login to their LEOE account online to view and enrol in a range of courses available to them based on their stage of life and whether they have met the prerequisite criteria. Ideally, the system would track attendance and recommend courses based on employment role, educational background, and account balance.
3. Individuals would review the details of the courses including the co-payment required to undertake it and opt into the course.
4. If the applicant meets all the requirements for a course, the approval would be instant, and the payment would be deducted from their account and sent to the institution directly. If the applicant does not meet all prerequisites, they will be offered the opportunity to appeal for special consideration. Such special requests will be reviewed by the central authority's case managers.

Some examples of the types of courses that could be covered by the LEOE education account include:

- **Childcare and pre-primary:** We envision the LEOE education account could help fund educational programmes for children ages 0 to 6 that are not currently publicly funded. For example, classes related to the cognitive and emotional or social development of children.
- **Primary and secondary:** Existing primary and secondary school curriculums differ widely from country to country and often take time to adapt to teaching the skills of the future. As such, we envision the education account could be used to fund extra-curricular activities, including music, language, sports, and technical skills. It could also be used for school camps, school leadership trips and other extra-curricular activities provided by their school or other institutions that teach similar social or emotional skills.
- **Higher education & vocational training:** The LEOE education account could be used to pay for higher education tuition fees. It could also be used to pay for courses outside universities, such as polytechnic, vocational, or other approved institutions.
- **Adult education:** With longer lifespans, more frequent career changes, and the varied demands placed on families, reskilling is a necessary component of the education system. Adult education could include a wide variety of courses both related and unrelated to one's profession, ranging from the arts to technical courses in cooking or mechanics to those related

to family responsibilities, such as caring for the elderly, childcare, and psychological counselling.

Conditions for Using the LEOE Education Account

To prevent abuse or fraud and encourage citizens to engage in learning, conditions could be applied to the education account. These include:

1. The education account could only be used for accredited courses or classes. For example, an institution may offer multiple courses, but only those courses which are accredited by the government would be published in the list and eligible for use of LEOE funds.
2. To prevent theft or misuse of funds by legal guardians, education funds would be designated to be used for the education expenses of the accountholder only, unless the accountholder is above the age of 18 and willingly transfers their education funds to another individual. Exceptional circumstances could be considered by case managers on a case-by-case basis.
3. Crucial to the success of this account would be incentives for completing education, especially for low-skilled or older workers. Incentives could include discounts on the price of certain courses when a certain number of hours have been completed or a top-up to the LEOE account upon completion of a course. The top-up reward could be transferrable to other spending accounts.

Reinforcing Policies for Education

To enhance the operation of the education account, a reinforcing policy that could be implemented is **increased investment in education from the private sector**. Governments could engage the private sector in the design of courses to ensure they are relevant to current and future job market needs, ensuring value for money.

Additionally, private companies, societies, organisations, and unions could be allowed to collectively enrol their employees or members in certain courses at a reduce fee. For example, if many employees in a company have children, the company could enrol employees in courses if they wish to take part in a childcare or children's mental health course. Labour unions could likewise enrol their members in skill upgrading courses to improve the productivity of their members. The fees in group purchase would be deducted from the individual's education account. Group registration could lower the cost for course providers and therefore reduce course fees relative to individual enrolment. Governments could also subsidise or cap the cost of courses to make them more affordable and accessible.

Healthcare

Introduction

Healthcare is a significant part of our lives from birth to death. The healthcare system handles care across four key areas: beginning of life, recovering from sickness, living with illness or disability, and the end of life. Across these stages, there are a set of principles that most healthcare systems strive to achieve as best practice:

Universality: Healthcare is seen as a universal right which all citizens and permanent residents can access. In Denmark immigrants and asylum seekers are also able to access the healthcare system if they are registered.²⁰

- **Accessibility:** The health system is accessible from a financial, geographic, and timeliness perspective. People can receive the services they require in a timely manner. For example, the first point of contact with the healthcare system is generally subsidised by the government or free of cost to ensure accessibility. Although general healthcare is a significant proportion of current government health expenditure in Europe, evidence suggests comprehensive primary healthcare reduces growth in overall healthcare expenditure over time and leads to a healthier population.²¹ This means it acts as a primary prevention mechanism against greater health costs later including potentially avoidable hospitalisations.
- **Efficiency:** It is vital that the health system in the country balances quality care with efficient delivery. Many countries have begun to use technology in delivery, information management, and coordination, especially during the COVID-19 pandemic. As a result, health systems have been more efficient and have reduced the costs of healthcare. For example, in the UK, primary care has shifted to a model of telehealth first whereby many patients are directed to engage in phone or video consultations prior to attending the clinic in a bid to reduce contact but also costs.
- **Quality care:** The care provided must strive to ensure a healthy population and one in which those with illness or disability are enabled to live fulfilling lives. This is a difficult aspect of the health system to measure and monitor but some strategies adopted by a range of countries include an accreditation system for healthcare providers and professionals. Some countries, such as Singapore, go a step further with a rigorous system for evaluating the quality of care through annual patient experience surveys and international external accreditations.²²
- **Focus on prevention:** The literature on health systems indicates the most effective method of reducing health care costs is preventive care, including public health information campaigns and pre-emptive testing for disease and illness. For example, evidence suggests testing for cervical and breast cancer has significantly reduced associated costs.

²⁰ Tikkanen, R., Osborn, R., Mossialos, E., Djordjevic, A. and Wharton, G. (2020). *International Profiles of Health Care Systems*. The Commonwealth Fund. <https://www.commonwealthfund.org/international-health-policy-center/countries>

²¹ Kringos, D. S., Boerma, W., van der Zee, J., & Groenewegen, P. (2013). Europe's strong primary care systems are linked to better population health but also to higher health spending. *Health Affairs*, 32(4), 686-94.

<https://www.proquest.com/scholarly-journals/europes-strong-primary-care-systems-are-linked/docview/1337184750/se-2>

²² Tikkanen, et al. (2020).

These best practices support the LEOE; however, they are not all mandatory and will depend on the political leaning of each country.

Basic Provision: Primary and Emergency care

Our model begins with some basic public health provision aligned with the notions of accessibility and universality above. The table below provides a high-level indication of some of the health services provided by public systems in Europe. Most European countries publicly finance the following services:

- maternity care
- primary and preventive care
- prescribed pharmaceuticals
- hospital and emergency care

Table 3: Example of Public Health Services in Europe

Country	Maternity care	Primary, hospital and emergency care	Prescribed pharmaceuticals	Physiotherapy and rehabilitation	Long-term/palliative care	Diagnostic services (tests and screening)	Dental care	Mental health care	Vision and hearing
Italy	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✓ <i>For children under 16 and vulnerable people</i>	✗	✗
France	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓ <i>For children</i>	✗	✗
Poland	✗	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	✗	✗	✗
United Kingdom	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓ <i>Some long-term care</i>	✓	✓ <i>Clinically necessary only</i>	✓ <i>Some including for those with learning disabilities</i>	✓ <i>For those assessed to need them</i>

✓ Covered for all ✗ Not covered

Sources: (1) Tikkanen, R., Osborn, R., Mossialos, E., Djordjevic, A., & Wharton, G. (2020). *International Profiles of Health Care Systems*. <https://www.commonwealthfund.org/international-health-policy-center/countries>; (2) Bukowski, H., & Pogorzelski, K. (2019). *Polish Healthcare Sector: Overview evolution and opportunities*. Netherlands Enterprise Agency and Innowo. <https://www.innowo.org/userfiles/publikacje/Polish%20Healthcare%20Sector.pdf>

Increasingly, some countries such as the UK, Denmark and Brazil also cover mental health care, dental services, and, in Germany, specialist services such as optometry. These decisions are generally made based on a trade-off between the cost of the treatment to the state and the estimated increase in quality-of-life years (QALY).²³ Each country has a view on this trade-off and our model does not dictate this decision; however, it is an important input into what is covered in the basic public provision of our model and how the LEOE healthcare account would be used.

LEOE Healthcare Account

The Lifetime Equal Opportunity Endowment does not aim to replace the existing healthcare system. We assume each country would continue to publicly fund their existing basic public health services as mentioned above ranging from maternity care to hospital and emergency care. Instead, the model would act as a complementary endowment that people could use for co-payment, insurance, or more costly operations, medicines and services not covered by the public system. In essence, the endowment in the model would be used to cover any *additional* out-of-pocket costs incurred by the individual related to their health.

The argument for an endowment for healthcare is to encourage individual responsibility over one's health and provide more choice on how and where their taxpayer funds are spent. The investment in human capital and healthier populations also has a compelling economic argument. If workforces are healthier physically and mentally, they are likely to be more productive, with positive spillovers for the economy and society as a whole.

It is important to ensure the system is not overburdened and overused simply because the government is co-funding healthcare provision and services through the LEOE. As such, a range of techniques often used by governments to manage the burden on public health systems could apply to this model as well, such as, co-payments, vouchers, rebates on proof of expenses, rising co-payments as the cost of healthcare rises, and medical insurance schemes.

Our model would allow for co-payment of healthcare expenses and would not be a 100% subsidised healthcare model. The LEOE is not large enough to completely fund all the healthcare expenses that are likely to be required by an individual over the course of their life. Instead, the endowment is there to incentivise increased savings and the uptake of services in the private healthcare system as people have more money to spend on their health, thus reducing the burden on the public system.

Table 4 provides an example of co-payment schemes that currently exist in Europe as well as any out-of-pocket caps on costs. These co-payment amounts could be increased to encourage the use of private healthcare systems and the LEOE healthcare account could be used to pay for these co-payments. This would in turn reduce the burden on the public healthcare system and welfare system.

²³ WWOEO, chapter 4.

Table 4: Examples of co-payment and out of pocket cost caps

Country	Co-payment		Out of pocket annual cap
Italy	Primary care:	€0	N/A
	Specialists:	€21 and €13 thereafter	
	Hospitals:	€0 with some fees for private	
	Prescription drugs:	€1 – 3 Class A drugs (generic and prescribed) Full price for Class C drugs (higher costs)	
France	Primary care:	€1 co-payment or up to €24 co-insurance €7.5 avg. patient fee	Co-payments capped at €50/year for physician visits, and another €50/year for nurse visits, transportation, medications, and physiotherapy <i>Exempt from all user charges:</i> maternity care, new-born care, and select preventive care <i>Exempt from coinsurance:</i> low-income households eligible for state-sponsored insurance; individuals with any of 32 chronic illnesses; and individuals on disability or work-injury compensation <i>Exempt from co-payments:</i> children and people with low income
	Specialists:	€1 co-payment or up to €29 –68 co-insurance €13.5 – 20.40 avg. patient fee	
	Hospitals:	€18/day co-payment 20% co-insurance	
	Prescription drugs:	€0.50/box co-payment 0 – 100% co-insurance depending on drugs	
Poland	Primary care:	€28 average spend	N/A
	Specialists:		
	Hospitals:		
	Prescription drugs:	PLN 3.20/ prescription 30% – 100% depending on drugs	
United Kingdom	Primary care:	£0	N/A
	Specialists:	£0	
	Hospitals:	£0	
	Prescription drugs:	£8.80/ prescription	
			No co-payment for young children, older adults, low-income people, and others Maximum out of pocket: £104/ year when annual prescription prepayment scheme is purchased, or £29.10 every three months for quarterly scheme

Sources: (1) Tambor, M., & Pavlova, M. (2020). Can people afford to pay for health care? New evidence on financial protection in Poland. World Health Organization. Regional Office for Europe.

<https://apps.who.int/iris/handle/10665/330606>; (2) Tikkanen, R., Osborn, R., Mossialos, E., Djordjevic, A. and Wharton, G. (2020). *International Profiles of Health Care Systems*. The Commonwealth Fund.

<https://www.commonwealthfund.org/international-health-policy-center/countries>

Conditions for Using the LEOE Healthcare Account

To ensure the effective delivery of the LEOE healthcare account, there are a range of conditions that countries should consider. These include:

- **Accreditation process and monitoring:** Agencies that accredit healthcare institutions currently in each country would provide similar accreditations to organisations that can be funded through the LEOE. They would also undertake audits to ensure compliance with the regulations for healthcare account spending. Additionally, governments would undertake evaluations and monitor health outcomes to ensure the spending is contributing to improved health outcomes.
- **Sharing of health account:** Per the general conditions listed above, individuals would be allowed to share the balance of their LEOE healthcare account with their nominated beneficiaries (spouses, parents, children, siblings etc.).
- **Health insurance:** Some countries have health insurance schemes, whether publicly funded by government or privately by employers or individuals. This pooling of risk in the healthcare system would be outside of this model; however, the healthcare account could be used to pay for this insurance.
- **Top-ups and case management:** People with disability are likely to spend more of their income and endowment on healthcare costs to ensure they lead a fulfilling life. As such, the LEOE healthcare account would serve as a receptacle for receiving enhanced health benefits due to disability while leaving current eligibility requirements for disability benefits unchanged.

Reinforcing Policies for Healthcare

As with any new system, there are a range of policies that would be required to ensure the LEOE healthcare account works as intended. These include:

- **Price caps:** Many countries have regulated caps on pharmaceutical prices, which are assumed to continue under this model. Price caps would need to be monitored closely as they are likely to rise once more people have money to engage in the private health system. It is counter-intuitive for the LEOE model's objectives if most of the endowment is simply spent on rising healthcare costs due to price hikes by pharmaceutical companies or private medical providers. As such, the government would need to maintain some price caps across a range of health products and services.
- **Pooled acquisition and sharing of risk:** The private sector could share in the risk and provision of healthcare of the workforce through employer-funded insurance schemes or the provision of employer-funded health services. For example, some companies now provide fully funded mental health support as evidenced by the rise in Employee-Assistance-Programs. Such schemes would lessen the burden on the public health system and on the LEOE health account.
- **Electronic health records:** Complementary to this model is a digital system in which electronic health records are kept, prescriptions are sent to pharmacies, and telehealth is a viable delivery option. A patient's health record would be linked via their digital ID to their LEOE healthcare account. This is to ensure a streamlined approach to managing co-payments and transfers.

Housing

Introduction

Research has shown the importance of location and proximity to opportunities to a person's quality of life, particularly their economic mobility and childhood development.²⁴ This makes housing a fundamental part of ensuring lifelong equal opportunity. However, obtaining, much less owning, a stable residence remains an economic challenge for many, even in high-income countries.

With increasing urbanisation and productivity outpacing wage growth, shortage of affordable housing is a pressing challenge, having reached a crisis point in many communities and forming a core impetus for reinventing the Welfare State.²⁵ Many families struggle to afford housing, often contributing up as much half their income to housing.²⁶ This is part of a general increase in the cost of basic necessities, which, as highlighted in *WVWEO*, has completely overtaken the income gains of the last two decades in some countries.²⁷

Housing policies, largely designed for a 20th century model of homeownership, have not adapted quickly enough to meet these challenges, often providing well-intentioned but ultimately distortionary responses.²⁸ Through provision of basic shelter and balancing of supply & demand for housing, our two-pronged model aims to make stable, quality, and affordable housing a reality for everyone.

Basic Provision: Guaranteed Basic Shelter & Adequate Supply of Permanent Housing

Housing policies can generally be divided into two categories:

- **Supply-side interventions** aimed at the provision or development of affordable housing; and
- **Demand-side interventions** focused on increasing individuals' ability to rent or purchase a home.²⁹

Affordable housing requires effective balancing of these supply- and demand-side policies. As such, our model makes supply-side policies the focus of basic provision by government to overcome market failures and achieve the policy objectives described below, with an LEOE account for housing serving as the mechanism for demand-side support. Our model sees these two elements being managed together in a coordinated manner.

The first component of basic government provision is **guaranteed access to and provision of basic shelter**. This would be based on a universal right to safe shelter and encompass shelters for the homeless and other models of temporary and supportive housing for those who lose their access to a permanent home or who need special accommodations, such as for physical or mental impairments.

²⁴ Chetty, R., Hendren, N., & Katz, L. F. (2016). The effects of exposure to better neighbourhoods on children: New evidence from the moving to opportunity experiment. *American Economic Review*, 106(4), 855-902.

<https://doi.org/10.1257/aer.20150572>

²⁵ Inchauste, G., Karver, J., Kim, Y. S., & Jehil, M. A. (2018). *Living and leaving: Housing, mobility and welfare in the European Union*. World Bank., pg. 14-15. <https://www.worldbank.org/en/region/eca/publication/living-and-leaving>

²⁶ Desmond, M. (2022). Unaffordable America: poverty, housing, and eviction. In E. J. Mueller & J. R. Tighe (Eds.), *The affordable housing reader* (2nd ed.). Taylor & Francis.

²⁷ *WVWEO*, pg. 102

²⁸ Inchauste, G., et al. (2018)., pg. 21.

²⁹ Caturianas, D., Lewandowski, P., Sokołowski, J., Kowalik, Z., & Barcevičius, E. (2020). *Policies to ensure access to affordable housing* (PE 652.729). European Union., pg. 37-42.

The rationale for government being the primary provider of shelter is because it serves primarily destitute individuals with little or no ability to pay and therefore would not be provided at the socially optimal level by the private sector. Additionally, given the positive spillovers of housing on a person's and also society's wellbeing, governments have a legitimate interest in ensuring consistent quality and universal access, which may not be achieved through patchwork charitable or private provision. This does not preclude governments from entering into public-private partnerships to deliver this housing and support services. Regardless of how a government chooses to deliver these services, the government would maintain primary responsibility for ensuring adequate basic shelter for all.

The second component of this basic provision is ensuring **adequate supply of affordable permanent housing** and refers to supply-side measures designed to ensure the amount of permanent housing meets demand at affordable prices. Such measures could take a variety of forms, including direct provision of social or public housing, land transfers, and incentives for private development. There are various examples of successful and replicable supply-side programmes in the European Union.³⁰ The particulars of such policies required by our model would depend on the local context, as housing market conditions (i.e., availability, norms/preferences, regulations etc.) vary significantly across countries and even communities. However, our model does rely on a universal goal of ensuring affordable housing by balancing aggregate supply and demand for housing.

Without adequate supply, demand-side measures such as housing subsidies have been shown to merely increase the price of housing by the amount of the benefit.³¹ For this reason, our model makes supply-side policies a first-order government provision and *condition* for the success of a complementary demand-side policy encapsulated within the LEOE.

LEOE Housing Account

Given the sizeable proportion of lifetime expenditure devoted to housing and its importance to financial stability and lifetime opportunity, we envision the LEOE being a **demand-side measure for preventing housing-related poverty** and complementing supply-side measures to **make housing affordable for everyone in society**. Practically, this could be accomplished through an LEOE account for housing with certain conditions. The design, generosity, and conditions for this LEOE account would depend both on the context of the implementing country as well as the unique circumstances/characteristics of the person using the funds.

Case managers would be essential to the success of this model in providing critical financial advice to LEOE accountholders and approving (where applicable) exceptions to conditions on the use of funds. This would require some level of bureaucracy, though we envision the capabilities of this bureaucracy could be revolutionized by technology to reduce administrative burden.

Conditions for Using the LEOE Housing Account

Due to limited funds and to prevent depletion of individuals' long-term savings, the ability to use LEOE funds for housing would likely come with some conditions/limitation. These include restricted eligibility to certain segments of the population who struggle to access housing or to specific housing-related expenses. For example, conditions could focus on first-time homebuyers/renters, the recently homeless, or those within a certain age bracket (e.g., age 30 or over). Funds could also

³⁰ Caturianas, D., Lewandowski, P., Sokołowski, J., Kowalik, Z., & Barcevičius, E. (2020). *Policies to ensure access to affordable housing* (PE 652.729). European Union., 37-42.

[https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2020/652729/IPOL_STU\(2020\)652729_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2020/652729/IPOL_STU(2020)652729_EN.pdf)

³¹ Ibid., 31.

be authorised only for certain types of expenses, such as down-payments/deposits, or in times of need, such as to cover rent/mortgage payments or utility bills during periods of unemployment.

To reduce misuse of funds and increase individual responsibility, account holders using LEOE funds for home loans could be required to refund their accounts with interest by a certain date or upon resale of their property, such as is required by Singapore's CPF regulations.³² Funds could be provided in a variety of ways beyond cash such as vouchers or rebates to reduce fraud and abuse as well as prevent further house price inflation. Additionally, account holders could be required to receive financial advice or case manager approval before funds are approved for use.

Reinforcing Policies for Housing

In the case of housing, top-ups could be given to provide additional support to disadvantaged groups (e.g., the disabled) and to incentivise certain surplus-enhancing behaviours. Examples of the latter could include allowing LEOE funds to be used for home insurance premiums³³ or matching of funds invested either individually or collectively in the renovating or restoring of homes (subject to application and approval). This would empower people and reward them for taking ownership of the maintenance and improvements of their dwellings (particularly in areas affected by blight), increasing the value of those homes for themselves and future tenants. Such policies could be implemented at the local, sub-national, or national levels.

³² Singapore Central Provident Fund, <https://www.cpf.gov.sg/member/home-ownership/using-your-cpf-to-buy-a-home>

³³ For instance, under the Singapore CPF, account holders in government-supplied housing are required to enrol in the national Home Protection Scheme, the premiums for which CPF funds are permitted to cover, though people are generally encouraged to fund those through private cash if possible.

Work Security

Introduction

As highlighted in *WWOEO*, improvements in technology, sectoral change, globalisation, and increased participation of women and other groups in the workforce have revolutionized the nature of work. While the Industrial Revolution initiated a shift from agricultural work to more steady employment in manufacturing and industrial sectors, globalisation and widescale adoption of information and communications technology (ICT) coupled with a reduction in labour regulations have again disrupted the employment landscape. Flexible and informal work arrangements are on the rise in developed countries as jobs that once provided long-term employment with benefits are increasingly outsourced or automated.³⁴

Like the Industrial Revolution, this Digital Revolution has brought both benefits and challenges. In many countries, the welfare state, born as a response to the Industrial Revolution, has not kept pace with this rapid evolution. Many of the underlying assumptions of the incumbent model (long-term, routinised employment requiring a basic education; family units provided for largely by an employed male breadwinner; and high union membership) are no longer the norms.

To take full advantage of the benefits accrued from the Digital Revolution, our proposed model seeks to **balance flexibility with security**, the fundamental policy objective proposed for work in *WWOEO*. Key to striking this balance is governments ensuring a minimum level of income security for all workers such that involuntary changes in employment or evolutions in the labour market do not pose significant danger to their health and wellbeing.

Basic Provision: Fair Labour Regulations, ALMPs, Industrial Policy, Macroeconomic Management

WWOEO describes the basic level of provision governments should guarantee: a minimum income to provide for shelter, food, and medical care; security for non-traditional, flexible work; and adaptation of policy to match the nature of the shock.³⁵ As it relates to work security, the ways in which a government can accomplish these goals are varied and encompass **labour regulations**, **work benefits**, and **industrial policy**.

For the purposes of our model, we define **labour regulations** as laws or policies governing the labour market without government funding (e.g., minimum wage laws, workplace safety regulations, anti-discrimination laws, etc.), whereas we define **work benefits** as entailing the provision of government funding. Four common types of work-related benefits include unemployment benefits, workfare (means-tested income support), active labour market policies (ALMP) (programmes aimed at helping workers obtain and retrain for jobs), and publicly funded paid leave. A third category of policies, **industrial policies**, may or may not entail government funding yet actively shape labour markets and the availability of good-paying jobs in a country by promoting vital industries, aligning skills training and education with emerging work opportunities, and incentivising training and innovations by firms.

As our model is adaptable to different economic contexts, it would depend to some extent on the implementing country which of these policies would be part of the basic provision of government versus provided through the LEOE or by employers. For example, paid leave policies vary from

³⁴ *WWOEO*, pg.98.

³⁵ *WWOEO*, pg. 107.

country to country. Another example is that in many high-income countries, unemployment insurance (UI) is the backbone of work benefits. However, this is not universal. Singapore stands out among its high-income peers in not offering any form of UI; instead, the government proactively shapes the labour market through industrial policy and ALMPs.³⁶ Other countries have a combination of these policies.

While allowing for some country-by-country variation, a shift from traditional models of employer-funded employment benefits to benefits provided by government through general taxation could help bring countries closer to the goal of balancing security with flexibility. For example, rather than taxing wages to fund unemployment insurance and other benefits (the cost of which tends to be passed onto workers in the form of lower wages³⁷) these benefits could be funded through general taxation and provided through a universal endowment, which this model proposes as an LEOE work security account.

LEOE Work Security Account

Reinforcing these basic government functions would be the LEOE as a tool for providing flexibility to workers. LEOE funds could be used as both individual 'piggy banks' for times of unemployment and leave or vehicles for workfare and economic stimulus.

Unemployment

As a consumption smoothing tool, the LEOE would help accomplish the balancing of security with flexibility in work called for in *WWOEO*, as funds deposited or accrued into individual accounts could be used in times of unemployment. Depending on the current work benefit offerings in a country, there need not necessarily be a unique LEOE account for work/unemployment-related expenses; rather, each person could withdraw from other accounts as needed, whether emergency funds to cover basic consumption of food or housing, use of education account funds for retraining, or use of housing funds to cover rent or mortgage payments.

LEOE has the potential to massively offset the need for UI, providing a portable safety net for workers while incentivizing savings and investments in the gaining of new skills. The degree to which LEOE funds would replace UI would depend on the set of programmes and policies currently offered in the country. For example, in a country like Singapore where UI is non-existent but ALMPs, industrial policies, and healthcare provision are robust, LEOE generosity (whether through accrual or top-up) could be less generous compared to a country with weak ALMPs and industrial policy and high rates of uninsurance in healthcare.

Paid Parental Leave

The LEOE could serve as a vehicle for universal paid parental leave, either replacing or supplementing employer-funded paid leave. Whether paid fully or partially by LEOE funds, having a universal system of LEOE-funded leave equally generous across genders would reap several benefits. Firstly, it would incentivise and normalise all parents to stay home and care for themselves and their children in the period after pregnancy and birth. This would even the playing field across genders and reduce hiring discrimination. Secondly, it would have additional benefits in prompting employers to compete for workers with more generous benefits or top-ups to guaranteed leave,

³⁶ New Zealand, one of the countries highlighted in *WWOEO* as an exemplar of effective balancing of flexibility and security, also does not have a UI system but is currently considering implementing one.

³⁷ Saez, E., Schoefer, B., & Seim, D. (2017) *The effects of employer payroll tax cuts on employment, business activity, and wages*. VoxEU. <https://www.voxeu.org/article/effects-employer-payroll-tax-cuts>

especially in strong labour markets. Simultaneously, it would ensure a basic minimum of leave in weak labour markets.

Conditions for Using the LEOE Work Security Account

While the receipt of €5,000 in LEOE funds annually from the government would remain unconditional, their use for any work-related purposes could adopt the same or different conditions used for work benefits currently. For example, funds could be made available only after a person formally files as unemployed with the appropriate government agency or upon approval by a LEOE case manager. Additional conditions or limits on funds could be applied based on age, income, how long someone has worked, intended uses of the funds, and whether job separation was voluntary vs. involuntary.

For funds spent on retraining and continuing education, the government could restrict funds to accredited courses and in addition provide cost-shares/matching of funds for programmes teaching skills most relevant to future workforce needs. This would help reduce abuse of the system, as has been seen with unconditional education vouchers in some countries, such as the UK and Singapore.³⁸

Reinforcing Policies for Work Security

Workfare

Many countries operate workfare programmes which supplement the incomes of low wage earners to enable them to make a living wage. The LEOE could be a vehicle for workfare, with income support deposited into LEOE accounts for conditional usage rather than into personal bank accounts for discretionary usage. This would accomplish the essential goal of workfare by enabling those making below a certain wage to save sufficiently for retirement and have the funds necessary to cover basic and emergency needs.

Economic Stimulus

Additional government top-ups into individual LEOE accounts could also be used as tools for economic stimulus in downturns as well as to incentivise retraining. Additionally, the reliance of the system on a digital ID infrastructure could help improve targeting of stimulus and poverty relief whilst reducing inefficiency and fraud (massive problems for many governments in their responses to the COVID pandemic) and consequently cost to the government.

Severance

One aspect of UI not previously mentioned which would not be fully captured with LEOE payments alone is preventing moral hazard on the part of employers (i.e., ensuring they fully pay the costs of layoffs). The U.S., for instance, applies a penalty ('experience rating') to employers based on the amount of unemployment benefits withdrawn by their employees.³⁹ The same goal could be achieved through additional policies utilising (or external to) LEOE accounts. For example, employers could be mandated to provide severance for terminated employees (other than for bad conduct), which would be deposited directly into workers' LEOE accounts.

³⁸ *WWOEO*, pg. 68

³⁹ U.S. Department of Labor. (2022). https://www.oui.doleta.gov/unemploy/pdf/uilaws_exper_rating.pdf

Pensions and Long-Term Savings

Introduction

The final component of equality of opportunity across a lifetime is ensuring that people have adequate income to cover their living costs after retirement. This is a key principle of reciprocity of the social contract in which people contribute to society during working years and then are cared for after retirement.⁴⁰ Investments for retirement also contribute to national productivity and economic growth.

Population ageing, most pressingly in Europe, is putting increasing financial pressure on governments to ensure access to an adequate pension in old age. This is leading to wavering trust in the pension system in some countries.

Mercer and CFA Institute's pension rating system is commonly used for assessing pension system health. This rating is based on three principles: **adequacy, sustainability, and integrity**. These principles guide the analysis and presentation of the pension component of our model.

In terms of pension design, there are multiple approaches to delivering these three key principles. The OECD categorises pensions according to three tiers as shown below.

Figure 5: Categories of Pensions Systems

Source: OECD. (2021). *Pensions at a Glance 2021: OECD and G20 Indicators*.

<https://doi.org/10.1787/ca401ebd-en>

The first tier is the first layer of social protection for old age and is mandatory and guaranteed by the state. This usually guarantees a minimum subsistence level pension for all people.⁴¹ In Europe, first-tier pensions currently provide benefits amounting to between 25-40% of average wages.⁴²

⁴⁰ *WWOEO*, chapter 6.

⁴¹ OECD. (2021). *Pensions at a Glance 2021: OECD and G20 Indicators*. OECD Publishing, Paris,

<https://doi.org/10.1787/ca401ebd-en>

⁴² *Ibid.*

Second-tier pensions are earnings-related and can be publicly or privately provided.⁴³ The focus of pension design has largely focused on second-tier pensions, as these can be preventative and incentivise individuals to save for retirement across their lifetime whilst sharing this risk with employers. Within second tier pensions, most countries have shifted away from defined benefit systems with pensions dependent on amount of years worked and earnings (which led to uncertainty with regards to cash flows for both governments and employers) and moved on to defined contribution systems in which individuals and employers contribute into individual accounts.

The average overall contribution rates for OECD countries is 15.4% (9.2% for employees and 6.2% for employers) with significant variations between countries, with Italy having the largest contributions at 33% compared to Lithuania at 9%.⁴⁴ Nevertheless, public spending on pensions has grown across the board from 6.6% to 7.75% of GDP between 2000 and 2017 in OECD countries, representing the largest social spending item (8.4% of total government expenditure in 2017 on average).⁴⁵ This raises sustainability concerns for current models.

Furthermore, in the defined contribution system, individuals bear the risks and opportunities of investment decisions. This has both advantages and disadvantages. On the one hand, research has shown that individual accounts and hence personal responsibility can have important behavioural effects incentivising savings.⁴⁶ On the other hand, low financial literacy can lead to poor investment decisions and thus the state needs to play a role in optimizing the architecture of investment options and ensuring the sustainability of the system.⁴⁷ Striking this balance can be difficult with implications for the adequacy and integrity of the pension system.

Best Practices

To address some of the current challenges faced in pension design, three important policy recommendations have emerged as suggested best practices.

- 1. Automatic adjustments:** As concerns over financial sustainability emerge, countries have adopted dynamic models in which benefit and contribution levels as well as the retirement age adjust to socioeconomic and demographic trends. For example, Italy has a notional defined contribution system that adjusts benefit levels according to economic growth forecasts and improvements in life expectancy.⁴⁸ This system of Automatic Adjustment Mechanisms (AAM) has been championed by international organisations like the OECD as a dynamic solution to the changing demands for a pension system that can fulfil all three principles.
- 2. Investment choice:** Most pension funds have favoured equity investments in retirement funds with a portfolio that is guided by the lifecycle; investing in riskier assets at a young age and safer assets at an older age.

Pension funds are increasingly offering options for individuals to choose to invest in more diversified and riskier investments; however, recent literature has favoured optimising rather than maximising in order to avoid the risks of poor investment decisions.⁴⁹

⁴³ Ibid.

⁴⁴ OECD (2021), *Pensions at a Glance 2021: OECD and G20 Indicators*, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/ca401ebd-en>

⁴⁵ Ibid.

⁴⁶ Tapia, W., and Yermo, J. (2007). *OECD Working Papers on Insurance and Private Pensions No. 11*. OECD. <https://www.oecd.org/daf/fin/private-pensions/39368306.pdf>

⁴⁷ Ibid.

⁴⁸ Ibid.

⁴⁹ N. Barr and P. Diamond. (forthcoming). *Better pension design*. Oxford University Press.

3. Liquidity: The liquidity of the pension fund is the last important component of pension design. Early withdrawals are usually heavily taxed, though recent trends in financial insecurity and the extraordinary circumstances of Covid-19 have led some governments to allow for withdrawals.⁵⁰ That said, withdrawals are usually restricted and regulated to prevent endangering the sustainability of the system. While the level of liquidity in retirement savings is very context-specific, special attention needs to be paid to balancing flexibility and sustainability of the system when it comes to withdrawals before the retirement age. In this sense, pension design is increasingly integrating mechanisms that allow for more flexibility and liquidity, and the individual pension fund increasingly takes on features of long-term savings.

For example, in the UK, the NEST, a workplace pension fund managed by the government, is experimenting with a liquid supplement to pension savings that allows individuals to withdraw funds up to a limit without tax penalties.⁵¹ This is an important advancement, as it allows individuals to prepare for catastrophic expenses such as a healthcare expense or other unexpected costs.

At retirement age, liquidity of the funds varies by country. Governments either favour self-management of defined contribution accounts or have the option for individuals to purchase an annuity which ensures a fixed income across the post-retirement lifetime. The latter allows for greater certainty and pooled insurance for the system, helping individuals to manage the risks of outliving their savings whilst improving the sustainability of pensions overall.

Basic provision: Adequate, sustainable, and trustworthy pension system

Our model begins with the state providing a sound regulatory framework that can ensure the pension system fulfils the three principles of adequacy, sustainability, and integrity. This includes defining the adequate level of pensions, introducing country-specific considerations (including fiscal policy, financial regulation, and necessary adjustments) to address sustainability, and good governance to ensure the integrity of the system. The state must also ensure that there are adequate incentives for risk-sharing between the individual, the employer, and the state. The basic provision of a sound regulatory framework for pension systems would ensure that the LEOE Pensions and Long-Term Savings Account could be used for its intended purposes and represent a true improvement from the status quo.

LEOE Pensions and Long-Term Savings Account

The pensions account in the LEOE would serve as a first-tier pension system ensuring a minimum state pension. While all LEOE spending accounts allow for investment in inflation-linked bonds and the housing account allows investment in real estate, the pension account would additionally allow individuals to diversify investment into equity in earlier years following the life cycle model. The pensions and long-term savings account would replace minimum pensions as a fixed endowment across lifetimes while at the same time have the possibility of integrating and becoming a default defined contribution pension fund.

Under this new model there would be a default minimum 10% of the LEOE to be assigned to the pension account and adjusted according to the lifecycle of the individual or according to a country's political considerations. As with traditional pension funds, the amount allocated to this account would be less liquid, have specific tax benefits, and have a set of investment options.

⁵⁰ OECD. (2021). *Pensions at a Glance 2021: OECD and G20 Indicators*, OECD Publishing, Paris.

⁵¹ NEST. Liquidity and workplace pensions: sidecar savings trial. NEST Pensions. <https://www.nestinsight.org.uk/liquidity>

The LEOE pensions and long-term savings account would not only be the default minimum guaranteed pension but also serve as a default defined contribution pension fund incentivising higher savings and investment and placing individuals and employers central to ensuring adequate and sustainable pensions. As the LEOE pensions and long-term savings account would allow investment in riskier assets, this would incentivise individuals to make additional voluntary contributions. If designated as the default defined contribution system for the workplace, it would enable employers to also make contributions to the employee's LEOE. This in turn would encourage long-term savings and increased personal responsibility over one's retirement funds.

Conditions for Using the Pensions and Long-Term Savings Account

Given the nature and purpose of the pensions and long-term savings account, there would be specific conditions pertaining to liquidity, investment, tax benefits, and generational transfers. These include:

- 1. Liquidity:** This account would be less liquid by design than other accounts within LEOE. The LEOE pensions and savings account would be the most restricted account with a fixed amount of the LEOE entering every year (subject to political and economic considerations) and with limitations for early withdrawals. As this account would also include long-term savings, governments could have specific provisions for capped withdrawals that can serve as last resort rainy day funds for individuals beyond what other LEOE accounts already provide.
- 2. Investment:** While the specifics of the investment options that could be offered through LEOE would vary by country, it is important that the pensions and savings account allow individuals to invest in equity early on. The conditions for this account would therefore focus on limiting the choice of investment options to assets that allow for risky investments whilst minimising risk. These pension and savings funds could use a combination of instruments and good governance criteria, such as limiting investments to those on an official domestic exchange, regulated by the domestic financial authority, and capitalized in the domestic jurisdiction. Lastly, the LEOE pensions/savings account would ensure investments are guided by the lifecycle, evolving from riskier to safer assets over time.
- 3. Tax benefits:** While we do not prescribe a specific tax benefit design, incentives to place money into a pension account usually include benefits, such as tax deferrals until withdrawal. The LEOE would have similar incentives to allow individuals, employers, and others to make additional voluntary contributions that can help grow the account.
- 4. Generational transfers:** Conditional on each country's regulations and values, unused pension funds could be transferred to family members or other individuals indicated on the beneficiary form. The amount would have an upper limit per individual transfer.
- 5. Top-ups:** If at retirement, an individual LEOE account does not have sufficient funds to cover the amount for a level of a minimum guaranteed pension as specified by the state, the government could provide top-ups to accounts when necessary and under prescribed conditions to ensure an adequate pension.

Reinforcing Policies for the Pensions and Long-Term Savings Account

To ensure the adequate delivery of the LEOE pensions and savings account, additional policies could be enacted that would enhance its operation.

- **Supplemental regulation of the pension funds:** The regulatory environment around publicly or privately managed pension funds, the role of employers, and withdrawals including the market for annuities varies significantly across countries. These are important implementation considerations and, while outside of the scope of this report, are supplemental policies for the LEOE pensions and savings account to be an effective model.
- **Adjustment mechanisms:** As highlighted above, an important consideration for the sustainability of the system is to adapt to the demographic and economic conditions of individual countries. This will be an important feature when implementing the LEOE pensions and savings account.
- **Financial education through technology:** For individuals to feel empowered and knowledgeable to invest their savings, policies supporting financial literacy would be essential. This could be delivered through online resources or educational classes.

Part V: Implementation and Feasibility

Whilst there are many frameworks to assess the implementation and feasibility of policy reform, Professor Lant Pritchett, in a discussion of the political economy of safety nets, offers a helpful framework in the context of implementing such programmes. In this model, the aim is to reach a solution which is not just technically correct but also *administratively feasible* and *politically feasible* (Figure 6).⁵² We believe the proposed model is a technically sound response to the challenges put forth in Part II of this report, so the next step is to discuss its administrative and political feasibility.

Figure 6: Elements of Policy Reform

Source: Pritchett, L. (2005). *The political economy of targeted safety nets*. Social Protection Discussion Papers and Notes 31498, The World Bank. <https://documents.worldbank.org/en/publication/documents-reports/documentdetail/283821468772779954/the-political-economy-of-targeted-safety-nets>

If a country were to adopt our model tomorrow, it would be a significant undertaking. As such, Lant Pritchett and others have advocated for taking a Problem-Driven Iterative Approach (PDIA) to policy reform, which focuses on locally driven, contextual, and iterative development. The PDIA toolkit developed by Harvard defines a “good problem” as one that:

- Matters to key change agents and therefore cannot be ignored;
- Motivates and drives change;
- Can be broken down into smaller parts;
- Allows real, sequential, strategic responses;
- Is locally driven, where local actors define, debate, and refine the problem statement through shared consensus.⁵³

⁵² Pritchett, L. (2005). *The political economy of targeted safety nets*. World Bank, Social Protection Advisory Service.

⁵³ Andrews, M., Pritchett, L., Samji, S., Woolcock, M. (2018). PDIA toolkit: a DIY approach to solving complex problems. Harvard Center for International Development. https://www.bsc.cid.harvard.edu/files/bsc/files/pdiatoolkit_ver_1_oct_2018.pdf

Reforming the welfare state is no doubt a ‘good problem’ according to this criteria. The PDIA framework resonates with our team as a suitable way to analyse the implementation of this model, given its emphasis on an iterative process and focus on sustaining authority and legitimacy.

Figure 7 shows the PDIA process, which could be adapted to fit each country’s context and the unique challenges and responsibilities required for implementing our model. ‘Locally-driven’ would mean driven both by the particular context of the implementing country as well as piloting and iterating the model in particular segments or sectors within the country. For example, implementing the LEOE health care account would undoubtedly require involving medical professionals, insurers, etc. in the process.

Figure 7: PDIA Process

Source: Andrews, M., Pritchett, L., Samji, S., Woolcock, M. (2018). *PDIA toolkit: a DIY approach to solving complex problems*. Harvard Center for International Development., pg. 7. http://www.bsc.cid.harvard.edu/files/bsc/files/pdiatoolkit_ver_1_oct_2018.pdf

Administrative feasibility

The following section delves into the administrative feasibility of the LEOE both from a structural standpoint and a financial perspective.

Structural

1. Reworking of the public sector and creation of a central agency

The LEOE would require expertise from a range of government departments as different policy areas are brought together. As such, the public sector may need to be rearranged and an agency would need to be established to manage and deliver the LEOE.

2. ‘Buy out’ endowment for all citizens, depending on their age, during transition

Implementation would involve a transition from an existing system to the LEOE. The state would need to provide a lump-sum amount to some citizens for the amount they would have accumulated from birth, under this new system. For example, this calculation may be a subtraction of each person’s use of the existing welfare system from the endowment they are entitled to depending on their age. These lump sum endowments would be essentially a book

entry on the balance sheet of the central agency, as initially most of the lump-sums would be immediately invested in inflation-linked bonds. It would however create a one-off increase in official government debt, substantially offset in later years.

3. Digital ID

A digital ID and infrastructure to manage payments to every citizen would need to be established for the operation of LEOE. This may require information campaigns, digital infrastructure spend, and cybersecurity spend. While many high-income European countries have a well-developed digital infrastructure, this initial outlay may be substantial in countries where the existing digital infrastructure is weak. There may also be challenges around the public's trust in the governments and in providing their personal information to the governments through the LEOE. However, the benefits of such a system for welfare management outweigh the initial costs by enabling generous lifetime endowment. Digitising the system would also allow many people who are often excluded from the system to access benefits such as people without a physical address or without other forms of identity.

Financial

One of the key questions of any welfare model is how it will be funded. Some high-level financial analysis using data from Italy, France, UK, and Poland is included in this section to sense-check the model against current welfare spending. However, the financial feasibility of this proposal will need to be explored in further detail with more specific analysis pertinent to each country.

We have three steps for testing financial feasibility, each one requiring more change than the last:

1. Reallocation of existing social spending by government
2. Funding via government revenue
3. Adjustments to the tax system

If a country can provide a sufficient endowment through the first step, then the remaining steps may not need to be followed. Ideally, the level of the endowment should initially be set so as to be tax neutral. These steps provide a range of ways in which LEOE could be funded.

The first step

The first step to testing financial feasibility is to reallocate existing social spend. This is a revenue neutral option in that it does not require an increase in taxes or government income.

A reallocation of existing government spending is, by definition, not more cost effective than the existing welfare model. However, this option may become more cost effective and efficient over time. This is because as people have more wealth from the annual endowment their need for public provision may fall, and they may move into the private system.

We believe this model will change attitudes towards public welfare provision from a 'use it or lose it' mentality in which people overuse the system due to the simple fact that it is not 'their' money, but the 'government's' money to one in which people have personal investment and ownership in their portion of welfare spending as an endowment. Therefore, it is highly likely there may be some efficiency gains in the use of the public system over time.

Table 5 provides an example of this step with select European countries. The figures are stipulated in USD for consistency across countries of analysis. If implemented, we would assume the endowment is in the local currency.

Table 5: Example of First Step in Sample of European Countries

	<u>Assumptions</u>	Italy	France	UK	Poland
<i>Endowment figure and as a % of GDP</i>	USD \$5,000	16%	13%	11%	32%
Total Endowment for country p.a.		\$295.33 bn	\$337.50 bn	\$336.63 bn	\$188.91 bn
GDP		\$1,861.28 bn	\$2,579.16 bn	\$3,111.10 bn	\$587.48 bn
Government total expenditure as % of GDP		57%	62%	51%	18%
Poverty Line (<i>Green if Endowment > poverty line</i>)		\$7,372	\$11,702	\$8,813	\$7,381

First step: Revenue neutral, with reallocation of existing social spending only

	<u>Proportion reallocated to Endowment</u>	Italy	France	UK	Poland
<u>Lifetime Equal Opportunity Endowment</u>			<u>% of GDP</u>		
Work (Unemployment)	100%	1.6%	2.6%	0.7%	0.7%
Pensions / Savings	100%	15.6%	13.6%	5.6%	10.6%
Education					
Pre primary	70%	0.5%	0.6%	0.6%	0.8%
Primary to Secondary	0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
Tertiary	50%	0.3%	0.6%	0.3%	0.3%
Healthcare	50%	3.2%	4.2%	4.0%	2.3%
Housing	100%	0.3%	1.1%	0.6%	1.9%
Total		21.5%	22.6%	11.7%	16.5%
Is LEOE financially feasible at the above endowment figure?		TRUE	TRUE	TRUE	FALSE

This model assumes all public spending on pensions, unemployment and housing subsidies are reallocated to the LEOE along with 70% of funding currently spent on pre-primary education and 50% of the funding spent on tertiary education. These reallocation percentages can be tweaked to suit the circumstances and political environment of each country and this modelling simply shows that for Italy, France and the UK tweaking existing spending whilst maintaining some basic public provision allows for a \$5,000 endowment.

For Poland, however, a \$5,000 endowment is not financially feasible simply by reallocating existing social spending as this endowment figure is 32% of their GDP and the reallocation in this manner provides funding of around 16.5% of GDP. This likely is a reflection of the smaller size of Poland's economy compared to the suggested endowment and therefore would require adapting the model with a smaller amount. In our calculations, a \$3,000 endowment represents 19% of Poland's GDP, which would be more feasible to implement in this specific country context.

The second step

If we assume existing social spend is insufficient, we may need to look at other costs that governments fund such as the public service, law and order, and public assets. It is helpful to understand if LEOE can be funded as a percentage of total government revenue and thus through an alteration of how total government revenue is spent, not just social spending. Total government revenue is 40% of GDP in Italy and France and approximately 35% in the UK and Poland.

Per our modelling, a €5,000 endowment, would equate to approximately 40% of total government revenue (or ~16% of GDP) in Italy, France, and the UK. This would leave 60% of government revenue for necessary services. Again, this is feasible in Italy, France, and the UK but not in Poland, where a reworking of the entire public sector to make it more efficient would be necessary or the endowment could be less generous.

The third step

The last step would be tax reform to fund LEOE. Many of the countries we have examined fund their existing welfare state through general tax revenue, income taxes, payroll or employer contributions and government insurance schemes. While an increase in the overall level of taxes is likely to be less politically feasible in Europe given that income tax revenue is a significant proportion of GDP (25% - 30% of GDP), there may be ways in which tax revenues could be increased via a fairer and more equitable distribution of taxes to fund the LEOE. For example:

- The simplification of the tax system in the form of one universal effective tax rate for all types of income, including employment income, capital gains, dividend, interest income and carried interest.
- Adjustment of the tax brackets
- The necessary elimination of the tax-free income allowance
- The increase of sales tax on non-essential products and luxury items
- The decrease of sales tax on food and essential items
- Changes to corporation tax to ensure all foreign income is taxed at an appropriate rate in the jurisdiction where the income is derived
- Tax incentives that encourage more personal savings in the LEOE
- Modest increase in levels of income and expenditure taxes

We have not modelled these options due to the complexity of tax systems in each country. However, we believe a reworking of the tax system and simplification should deal with a significant problem of the current system that affects welfare. Namely, that the effective marginal tax rate at the lower end of the income distribution is often the highest as a proportion of total income as incremental income often leads to a loss of welfare benefits. These changes would make the tax regime fairer for all whilst potentially increasing personal savings and the total government tax revenue collected.

Political feasibility

In terms of political feasibility, our model is no doubt ambitious, as it not only would reinvent the structure of the welfare state but also likely require a high degree of trust in government and coordination across state actors to accomplish. First, countries would have to be interested in reforming their welfare state. Then, there would have to be buy-in from both the government and the electorate to sustain the change. However, there are aspects of the model which could make it both appealing and feasible.

Appeal Across the Political Spectrum

While the welfare state has often been a target of right-wing parties, this model, with its balancing of flexibility and security and emphasis on personal responsibility along with a national endowment, could be appealing to members of both the left and the right. The left would be attracted to the guaranteed basic provision as well as the breadth of the LEOE to cover a range of expenses across one's lifetime, while the right would like the shift toward greater personal responsibility and choice. Both political spectrums should find the individual customisation of welfare provision and the discernment around an individual's welfare spend appealing to their political base. Governments wishing to implement this model would benefit from emphasizing these features in promoting this policy change.

Fairness

It is also important that such a model be fair and be seen as fair by the electorate. While there can and likely should be some progressivity in the funding of this model, what an individual gets out of the model should generally be seen as fair for what they put in and given their particular circumstances. This of course would mean that the most disadvantaged (e.g., the disabled, young children) would receive more than they have contributed but society as a whole would be better off.

Piecemeal Implementation

While this model requires first order basic provision and second order endowment components in order to function effectively, this is not to say that an LEOE-style endowment could not be implemented gradually. For example, a smaller endowment specifically for education or for childcare or for health care could be piloted to test behavioural responses and efficacy.

Bureaucratic Reform

Another area in which we anticipate challenges is in the restructuring of the government bureaucracy, as government workers might resist such a massive change to their work and possible layoffs. As such, it would be important to invest in retraining and retooling of the public labour force where possible.

Part VI: Recommended Reinforcing Policies for the Model

To support the operation and functions of LEOE, the following policy recommendations need to be considered:

Pre-redistribution policies

Minimum wages

The minimum wage is designed to protect the basic needs of employees. A fixed annual amount for each citizen from LEOE certainly meets the basic needs of everyone but this does not conflict with the minimum wage. The minimum wage still needs to be guaranteed in order not to affect the functioning of labour market policies. Two aspects are worth noting:

1. It is important that minimum wages are not set too high because those workers who are not productive enough to justify the minimum wage level may end up unemployed.
2. The minimum wage may need to be adjusted in light of the implementation of LEOE. Workers will lose motivation to work if the LEOE and the minimum wage together keep individuals well over the bare necessities of life. The minimum wage policy needs to be properly adjusted so that the introduction of the LEOE does not reduce people's incentive to work.

Access to technology

The LEOE integrated fully would require access to the internet and computers. For example, many courses or consultations could be held online in the fields of education and healthcare. Every citizen has to have access to networks and devices. There are various methods for doing this:

1. Granting individual subsidies to guarantee that every citizen has access to the internet and a device to access it, depending on the financial state of that country;
2. Establishing a public computer centre (e.g., each community could have a public library or office where residents could use computers and access the internet for free); and
3. Setting up a system for people to borrow devices with internet access from a community office.

Labour market participation

Policies that enable and support the expansion of the labour market participation are key in ensuring the sustainability of the model. Policies that encourage women to work, as highlighted in this report and in *WWOEO*, would have consequential impact on the sustainability of the model with potential to increase productivity and growth and expand the tax base, thereby increasing funding for the welfare state. Policies that furthermore address informality and underemployed individuals are also necessary for the LEOE to be effective.

Taxation policies

Taxation is a major and critical supporting policy for the introduction of LEOE. As an equal opportunity-oriented model, the LEOE must be built on tax policies that:

- **Reduce the incidence of poverty traps:** The taxation of income regime should start at zero and apply from the first dollar of each person's income according to the tax rate.
- **Are fair:** After adding up all of an individual's sources of income (see above), everyone should be taxed at the same rate.

In the case of corporations, domestic and foreign corporations operating in the jurisdiction should be subject to sales tax on the sale of their products in the domestic economy.

- **Encourage the creation of wealth, savings, and self-responsibility.**
- **Allows for inheritance and transmission of wealth to the next generation.**

Regulatory environment

Accreditation of institutions

The government would need to implement a robust accreditation and compliance system for all institutions involved in the LEOE system, whether public or private institutions.

Security, risk, and anti-corruption

Safeguards are necessary to protect LEOE accounts from several risks. If there is a risk of theft or compromise of an account, the central agency would need to ensure that such issues are addressed in a timely manner. To avoid corrupt practice in the LEOE, regulations need to ensure that if a public official assists a user in converting impermissible LEOE account funds to cash in any way, the public official and the account holder should face prosecution.

Price control

After the introduction of the LEOE, every citizen will receive what amounts to a stimulus every year. With more money at everyone's disposal, regulation should ensure that the prices of goods and services available for LEOE do not rise disproportionately.

Engaged populous

Civic education in schools

Ensuring that everyone receives civic study in their formal education is key to building the trust, personal investment, and informed decision-making needed to ensure the model's success. People need to know what their roles as citizens are and what rights they are entitled to. The goal of civics course would be to prepare people to become knowledgeable and proactive members of a society. Such instruction would be universally accessible to everyone as a public provision.

Duty of care over public assets

This policy refers to conservation, planning, and management of public assets and infrastructure, including city layout and architecture, as well as parks, museums, and transportation. The sense of having lifetime equal opportunity would be enhanced by governments taking a duty of care over these public assets. All citizens need to derive equal enjoyment from the use of, and the aesthetic of, public spaces and assets.

Governments need to ensure that these assets are protected while being accessible and enjoyable by all. It is also vital to make sure that each community or region has well-maintained public facilities. In Singapore, for example, every neighbourhood is outfitted with a supermarket, shopping centre, garden, children's playground, library, train/bus station and religious establishments within a certain radius.⁵⁴ Although this is already the situation in many European countries, it is the duty of the government to guarantee a standard for these public amenities.

⁵⁴ Heng, C. (2016). *50 years of urban planning in Singapore*. World Scientific Publishing Co Pte Ltd.

Happiness Index or Wellbeing Budget

In addition to adopting the LEOE, we recommend European welfare states consider developing a 'wellbeing budget' to address the needs of people's wellbeing both within and external to the welfare state. An interesting example in this regard is the New Zealand Wellbeing Budget, which is founded on the notion that financial prosperity alone is not a sufficient measure of the quality of life.⁵⁵ We envision national budgets that are not created solely around economic indicators like GDP but also include a wider, more holistic range of wellbeing indicators, such as employment, housing, safety and prosperity, and environmental sustainability.

⁵⁵ Mintrom, M. (2019). Is New Zealand's wellbeing budget worth all the hype? Centre for Public Impact. <https://www.centreforpublicimpact.org/insights/new-zealands-wellbeing-budget-worth-hype-contributor-michael-mintrom>

Part VII: Conclusion

In *What We Owe Each Other*, Minouche Shafik offers a timely analysis of why a new social contract is necessary to achieve shared prosperity in an increasingly complex, globalised world. This report has sought to build on her work by proposing a new model for the welfare state which has the potential to address the challenges outlined in her book and balance flexibility with security, personal responsibility with mutual obligation.

Our hope is that the model we have described in this report will catalyse and assist further research on the design of a more effective social safety net as part of the broader LSE project to reimagine the state. We see country-specific analysis and stress-testing by both academics and policymakers of the validity of this proposed model as logical next steps in this process. We hope that this provocation for a new welfare state will provide the impetus to create a social contract that values and provides lifelong equal opportunity.